

GESTURES IN THE SYSTEM OF PARALANGUAGE

Saydikramova Umida Xamidullayevna

Named after Islam Karimov

Tashkent State Technical University

Teacher of the Foreign Languages Department:

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Abstract: Language gestures are communicative systems, the expression plan of which is not based on acoustic, as in sound languages, and on the kinetic (gestural-mimic) basis. It is widely believed that in the process of glottogenesis gestures the languages preceded sound languages. Gesture languages are the main, and often the only means communication of the deaf. In many regions, the languages of the hearers were also common; their existence is noted in the Americas, Africa, Australia, Oceania, India, the Caucasus, the Mediterranean. Among the Gestures, the languages that hear the most well-known gestures of Aboriginal languages Australia and North America.

Key Words: language, paralanguage, paralinguistic, young, gestures.

The widespread use of sign language among Australians are associated with the ritual silence of young men during initiation rites and widows in a period of mourning, lasting for some tribes for up to a year or more. Language gestures they are also used for distance communication, for keeping silence on the hunt. The territory of the spread of individual gestures of the languages of Australians does not coincide with Ethnic and linguistic boundaries. These gesture languages are described insufficiently; words of a number of languages have been published (from a few dozen to several hundred gestures), grammatical observations are single. In the North American prairies, a single gesture was widely spoken, used mainly in interethnic communication. According to some information, at the end the 19th century it was owned by over 100 thousand people. The lexical composition of this language gesture is described the grammatical structure has been studied poorly. Linguistic study of gestures languages, started by W.K. Stokou in the 50's of the 20th century, especially intensified since the 70s, there appeared periodicals on the gestures of languages. Many researchers pointed out that humans as a biological species conserve to itself signs of an animal character and in system of means of communication (tactile, visual, even chemical systems), but all these forms, first, there are Scholasticians simultaneously with the sound language, and secondly, it is never replaced. Besides, the gestural system, for example, does not have a human character, it is abstract and universal in contrast to the action of signaling in animals, determining the purely concrete behavior of the individual

(halt, danger, etc.).¹ Non-linguistic human communication systems are subordinate, secondary systems, but, despite the most diverse of their origin, they are functions only adhere to the language, are used by the language and decoded using language. This gives grounds not to consider these systems as independent to see in them structurally organized system, and not the auxiliary tools used sound language. In this sense, all paralinguistic means can be combined only by its function, i.e. on the function of participation in the formation of information of the speech statements, and not by their material status. The same material forms "Non-verbal behavior" of a person, on the one hand, should considered paralinguistic, and on the other hand - by any other branch of science (for example, genetics, etc.). From this point of view, the study of gestures can be carried out in aspects: biological, cultural-historical, ethnographic and paralinguistic.² For a linguist it is important in all cases to draw a clear line between paralinguistic and biological functions of these funds. Along with a broad situational paralinguistic context, oral communication widely uses the typed, physical manifestations of the speaking subject directed to the orientation of the listener to unambiguously perceive the utterance. These means are primarily gestures and facial expressions. Adopted gesture definitions different kinds of gestures are involved; Kinetics, and the facial expression person speaking. In general, kinesika is a division of biological science by origin and should enter into zoosemiotics, if by the latter one understand the science of a certain system of expression of the physiological states of the animal. Semiotic in this plan will be only a conventionally allocated stereotype of some movements, this or that biological state of the animal. However, this stereotype does not have the ability to transmit any non-biological values. It is clear that the vast majority of man's kinetic manifestations as a part the animal world will also be at the level of its purely biological organization. Only certain movements, and above all the movement of the hand as an organ, do not medically employed in the labor process, are considered as some subsystem language communication as an auxiliary function for the identification of an unambiguous verbal act (replenishment of the Ellipse, elimination of the polyseme). This is why paralinguistic kinesics can be considered as a part of language communication, peculiar only to man, and that's why it should be identified as a special part of the "kinetic" behavior of a person. Countless examples of the use of paralinguistic means in verbal communication

¹ Stokoe. W. Semiotics and Human Sign Languages. Mouton. The Hague, 1972.

² Верещагин. Е.М. Вопросы теории речи и методики преподавания иностранных языков. М., 1969, гл.4.

gives fiction, where the description of the dialogue, as a rule, is constructed in relation to the conditions of natural communication, i.e. To the paralinguistic context. “Voinitsky: *Give me something ...*”(pointing to his heart). Burns here. “(A.Chekhov. Uncle Ivan.). (А.Чехов. Дядя Ваня.) In the dialogue: “Borkin. ... *so you do not get married?* Shavelsky (*shrugs his shoulders*). *is he Seriously ... Amazing person*”(A. Chekhov. “Ivanov”). The question is unambiguously deciphered: “*So you do not marry?*” becomes explicitly a form of rhetorical question thanks to gesture (*shrugs*), and then the phrase describing this character can be correctly understood (*Amazing human!*). It should be noted again that in these funds it is necessary to conduct the dividing line between gestures and facial expressions, and between kinesics, accompanying speech on a purely physical and biological level. Gestures and kinesics can be seen in the field of communication as ancillary functional component. In this matter, we can recall the statement of Balin connection with its interpretation of the actualization function in relation to paralinguistic means: “A sign that represents an actual concept can have a mimic character, i.e. be any arbitrary movement serving to indicate: by gesture hands, movement of the head, direction of eyes, etc. If, for example, pointing to premit finger, *I say: Doppesz. “Give!*”, Then my gesture supplements the proposal, which is equivalent to the sentence: “*Give me a thing that is there*”; This gesture is actualized, those grammatical links connecting the virtual concept of things with the subject to which she points: Sh. Bally considers in general these means-signs (including deictic) in the background regularities in the formation of real speech utterances, but most importantly, he notes, is their functional connection with the structure of the utterance. A vivid illustration of the paralinguistic use of gestures, facial expressions is

Reading actor:

Furnachev. *How great is the capital of the most respected Ivan Prokofievich?*

Zhyznoydov. *Great, monsieur, great ... you cannot even figure out how big it is. So I believe, that one million for two will be.*

Furnachev. *This should be assumed, madam ...*

In the text of the play, there is no remark or underscore, but the artist found it here culmination of the stage situation. After the words Zhivoyedova about two million to him as if blood hit his head, he felt unwell, his breath froze in his throat, such Tetanus found him, that the audience unerringly burst out applauding, and in this state of tetanus, the artist stayed with a minute, then fell, fell, translated breathing, and, with a furious gesture taking out the foulard's

handkerchief, erased the sweat from his forehead - and walked the secondary shaft of applause. A very clear illustration of the very close interaction of sound speech and Paralinguistic means is the speech of actors in a silent movie. Although a silent cinema has its own specific laws and peculiarities, but one cannot, nevertheless, assert that the absence of verbal utterance in the form of sound (it should be taken into account that the orientation actors silent film is very clear, expressive and the viewer can perceive by guessing words) transforms speech into a somewhat unnatural plan of use paralinguistic phenomena. On the one hand, the entire role of gestures and facial expressions in the absence of sound is reinforced by the whole system of actor's play for disclosure meaning and purpose of the action of the characters for the audience. In terms of paralinguistic is very interesting. It would be learning how to act in a silent movie, which in addition to art interest, would have a practical meaning for the authors involved in duplication of films from foreign to native language. In terms of the origin of the language, all types of gestures and facial expressions of man were originally purely biological phenomenon (for example, a certain movement of the hand as a defensive measure, etc.). This provision has long been developed in linguistics and related sciences .Another Ch. Darwin wrote: "The ability of members of the same tribe to communicate between themselves, with the help of the languages of language, was of paramount importance in the development of the person; Expressive same movements of the face and body greatly contribute to the power of the language ...

Less, as far as can be seen, there is no reason to believe that any muscle has developed or even changed solely for the sake of expression. On the contrary, every ... expressive the movement had some natural and independent origin ".³ For the perfect state of the language, the biological nature of a certain part of these means has outgrown and transformed into a paralinguistic phenomenon. Actually paralinguistic means are isolated from the sphere of extra linguistics, on the grounds that they are a subsystem of conventional means.

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³ Charles Darwin. Collected works. III. M., 1908, p. 204-205

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